

Effects of thermal treatment on micro-Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ solar cells prepared by one-stage selenization of sputter Cu-In-Ga precursor

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Abstract

Micro-concentrator photovoltaics combine sub-millimeter scale solar cells with optical concentrator systems, enabling higher power conversion efficiencies, material savings, and improved heat management. In this work, we investigated the effects of thermal treatment of Cu-In-Ga precursors on Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ micro solar cells. The devices were fabricated by sputtering a Cu-In-Ga precursor onto a soda-lime glass/SiO_xN_y/Mo/SiO_x pre-structured substrate with micro-holes of 200 and 250 μm diameter, defined by photolithography. The precursor undergoes thermal treatment at 450 °C, followed by selenization at 480°C. The treated Cu-In-Ga exhibited a smoother surface, with indistinct grains, compared to the as-deposited film. However, areas of exposed Mo were observed upon treatment. After selenization, the treated micro-absorber exhibited improved elemental composition with Cu to (Ga+In) ratio of 0.81±0.06, compared to 0.76±0.13 for the untreated micro-absorber. Electrical characterization of the devices revealed better overall performance for the treated Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ micro solar cells, with an average V_{oc} of (239±26) mV, significantly higher than the (176±25) mV achieved by untreated micro cells.

1. Introduction

Over the past 50 years, environmental concerns have increased significantly, particularly regarding the impact of energy production, transformation, transportation, and consumption, exacerbated by population growth, energy demand, and industrialization [1]. Electricity is essential for societal living standards and development, with global access increasing from 87% in 2015 to 91% in 2021, benefiting 800 million people. However, 685 million people remained without access to electricity in 2022 [2,3]. Solar energy is a key solution to the global energy crisis, offering a clean, safe, abundant and sustainable resource [4]. In 2023, photovoltaics represented over 75% of new renewable electricity technologies installed, reaching a cumulative capacity of 1.6 TW [5]. Silicon-based solar cells dominate the market, comprising 97% of global photovoltaic production in 2023 [6]. Crystalline silicon (c-Si) solar cells have reached record power conversion efficiencies (PCE) of 27.3% for silicon heterojunction, 26.1% for monocrystalline, and 23.3% for multicrystalline silicon solar cells [7]. Thin-film technologies, e.g., cadmium telluride (CdTe) and copper indium gallium selenide (CIGSe), offer cost-effective alternative to traditional c-Si, with record efficiencies of 23.1% [7] and 23.6% [8], respectively.

To enhance efficiency, new photovoltaic technologies and architectures have been explored [9–13], including concentrator photovoltaics (CPVs). CPV systems use optical components to

1 concentrate solar irradiance onto smaller, high-efficiency solar cells, enabling the use of more
2 expensive materials while potentially achieving a levelized cost of electricity (LCOE)
3 competitive with conventional flat-plate photovoltaic technologies. [14]. CPV has achieved
4 remarkably high efficiencies, with current records of 30.8% at 61× for flexible single-junction
5 GaAs, 47.6% at 665× and four-junction GaAs concentrator solar cells, and 23.3% at 14.7× for
6 thin-film CIGSe [15–17]. However, CPV presents challenges, including thermal management,
7 inability to collect diffuse irradiation, and dependence on tracking mechanisms.

8 To overcome these limitations, micro-concentrator photovoltaics (μ CPVs) have been
9 intensively investigated due to their potential advantages over conventional CPV technologies
10 [18], including enhanced PCE, reduced material consumption [19,20], improved thermal
11 management [21], and flexibility in the system architecture and design [22–24]. μ CPV
12 technology miniaturizes solar cells to an area smaller than 1 mm², combined with a micro-
13 optical system with diameters ranging from a few millimeters to a few centimeters [24].
14 Significant progress has been made in CIGSe μ CPV, demonstrating the feasibility through
15 both top-down [25,26] and bottom-up approaches [27,28]. In the top-down fabrication, co-
16 evaporation is typically employed, yielding high-quality CIGSe micro-absorbers with reported
17 PCEs ranging from 11 % to 16% under 1 sun, and up to 21% under concentrated illumination.
18 For instance, co-evaporated CIGSe microcells fabricated via photolithography after buffer
19 layer deposition, achieved a PCE of 16.3% under 1 sun, increasing to 21.3% at 475× [20].
20 Conversely, bottom-up techniques such as electrodeposition [29], thermal evaporation of In
21 precursors [27,28] and laser-induced forward transfer [27], have resulted in significantly lower
22 efficiencies, typically below 6% under both standard and concentrated illumination conditions.
23 Furthermore, bottom-up micro-CIGSe devices fabricated by electrodeposition into patterned
24 substrates, reached a PCE of 3.5% under 1 sun and 5.2% at 3× [29]. Recently, Poeira *et al* [30]
25 reported a new approach consisting in sputtering of Cu-In-Ga (CIG), followed by lift off and
26 subsequent selenization. Focusing on morphological characterization, they found that a thermal
27 pre-treatment leads to more compact micro-CIGSe dots, presumably resulting from the
28 removal of photoresist remnants incorporated in the CIG precursor. Here, we optimize the
29 thermal treatment studying the structural properties by Raman spectroscopy and XRD and
30 assess the impact on the photovoltaic performance of micro-CIGSe absorber.

31 In this study, micro-CIGSe solar cells were fabricated by sputtering a CIG precursor onto a
32 soda-lime glass (SLG)/SiO_xN_y/Mo/SiO_x pre-structured substrate with micro-holes of 200 and
33 250 μ m diameters, defined by photolithography. We investigate the effects of thermal
34 treatment on micro-CIGSe solar cells, where the CIG precursor was annealed at 450 °C
35 followed by one-stage selenization in a tube furnace to form the CIGSe absorber, without any
36 post-deposition treatment (PDT) for Na incorporation. Electrical characterization of the
37 devices reveals an average improvement of 64 mV in V_{oc} for the treated absorber, with the best
38 micro solar cell achieving a PCE of 1.44 %.

39 **2. Materials and methods**

40 *2.1 Fabrication of micro-CIGSe solar cells*

1 The fabrication started with the deposition of a 100 nm thick SiO_xN_y Na barrier by radio-
2 frequency (RF) magnetron sputtering, followed by standard 500 nm thick Mo back contact
3 bilayer on a SLG substrate. For micro-structuring, the SLG/ SiO_xN_y /Mo substrate undergoes
4 standard cleaning in an ultrasonic bath with acetone, and isopropyl alcohol and deionized water
5 rinses. A 2 μm thick SiO_x layer was then deposited via plasma-enhanced chemical vapor
6 deposition (PECVD). Next, a 2200 nm thick positive photoresist layer was spin-coated onto
7 the SiO_x layer, patterned by direct write laser (DWL) exposure and developed. Reactive ion
8 etching (RIE) was employed to etch the micro-holes through the SiO_x layer until the Mo back
9 contact is exposed. A detailed description of the pre-structured substrates fabrication can be
10 found in [31].

11 The CIG precursor was deposited via direct current (DC) magnetron sputtering onto structured
12 SLG/ SiO_xN_y /Mo/ SiO_x /resist substrate stack using a CIG ternary target (50:35:15 at%) in the
13 STAR system [32] at 1.5 W/cm^2 power density, under a working pressure of 5.6×10^{-3} mbar.
14 The resist was then removed by a lift-off process with acetone, leaving a SiO_x layer matrix with
15 CIG micro-dots. The removed CIG material can be subjected to metal separation and recovery
16 [33–35]. For the thermal treatment, the sample was placed inside a vacuum pot, which was
17 placed on a heating plate. To prevent contamination, at least three cycles of nitrogen purging
18 and pumping were performed before heating. The hot plate was set to a nominal temperature
19 of 450 °C and kept for 30 min once the target temperature was reached.

20 The CIG precursors were selenized in a tube furnace inside a graphite box with 50 mg of
21 elemental Se, loaded inside a quartz tube. To minimize oxygen contamination, the tube
22 underwent five purge and pump cycles - three with N_2 , and two with Ar. A single-stage
23 selenization was performed at atmospheric pressure under Ar flow at 480 °C, with a heating
24 rate of 10 °C/min for 30 minutes. Once the process was finished, the furnace remained closed
25 and was cooled down below 130 °C, at a cooling rate of 20 °C/min. The selenized films were
26 etched in a 5 wt% KCN aqueous solution for 30 seconds to remove any Cu- Se_2 phases,
27 followed by CdS buffer layer deposition at 60 °C via chemical bath deposition. For electrical
28 characterization, the micro solar cells were isolated using Kapton tape stripes to create a matrix
29 of micro-absorbers prior to window deposition. Window layers, i-ZnO and ZnO:Al, were then
30 deposited by RF magnetron sputtering [36]. For clarity, the untreated sample is referred to as
31 S0, while the thermally treated sample as S450.

32 *2.2 Characterization techniques*

33 The micro-CIG precursor and CIGSe morphology and composition were determined by
34 scanning electron microscopy (SEM) in a FEI Quanta 650 FEG microscope equipped with
35 energy dispersive X-ray diffraction (EDX) using acceleration voltages of 10 kV for surface
36 analysis, and 20 kV for bulk analysis. Raman spectroscopy of the micro-CIGSe was conducted
37 using a Witec Alpha 300 R confocal Raman system with a laser power of 3mW at 532 nm and
38 a 1800-line grating.

39 The crystalline structure of a CIG precursor deposited on a SLG/ SiO_xN_y /Mo substrate without
40 structuring, before and after thermal treatment, and of the resulting CIGSe absorber, were
41 investigated by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using Cu-K α radiation in a Panalytical X'Pert Pro-

1 MRD system processed in HighScore software. The XRD data were then subjected to analysis
2 and the crystallite size was estimated using the Scherrer equation: $D = K\lambda/(\beta \cos\theta)$, where D
3 denotes the size of the crystallites, K is the Scherrer constant (a value of 0.9 was used for the
4 shape factor), λ is the wavelength of X-rays ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$), and β is the full width half
5 maximum (FWHM) of the diffraction peak at the Bragg's diffraction angle θ .

6 Current density-voltage (JV) characteristics of the micro-devices were assessed in an Oriel
7 Sol3A class AAA solar simulator under 1.5 AM illumination. The devices were measured
8 without a front grid at room temperature.

9 **3. Results and discussion**

10 *3.1 Characterization of as-deposited and thermally treated CuInGa precursor*

11 The surface morphology of the as-deposited CIG precursor shows a rough surface with In-rich
12 island-like grains (Fig. 1a). EDX mapping was performed to analyze the spatial distribution of
13 the In content, confirming its high concentration in the grains (Fig.1b). When thermally treated,
14 the grains become indistinct, resulting in a smoother surface compared with the as-deposited
15 precursor. However, SEM imaging revealed areas of exposed Mo, confirmed with EDX
16 mapping (Fig.1c-d). This Mo exposure may be attributed to (1) the degassing of residual resist
17 incorporated within the CIG film during deposition [30], or (2) intrinsic stress caused by
18 structural changes within the film, at the CIG/Mo interface and CIG/SiO_x micro-hole
19 structures, or at the film surface [37]. In terms of composition, bulk analysis indicate that the
20 as-deposited CIG precursor is Cu-poor, with [Cu]/([Ga]+[In]) (CGI) and [Ga]/([Ga]+[In])
21 (GGI) ratios of 0.75 ± 0.04 and 0.24 ± 0.03 , respectively. After thermal treatment, a slight
22 decrease in both ratios was observed. In contrast, surface measurements of an as-deposited
23 micro-precursor show a Cu-rich surface, with CGI and GGI ratios of 1.14 and 0.31,
24 respectively. Meanwhile, bulk composition indicated a Cu-poor film, with CGI of 0.79 and
25 GGI of 0.24, within the average values observed. However, after thermal treatment, no
26 significant variation was observed, with GGI of 0.20, and a Cu-poor surface and bulk with CGI
27 ratios of 0.77 and 0.75, respectively. Surface measurements on different points of as-deposited
28 and treated precursors revealed compositional variations within the films' surface, as shown in
29 Fig. 1e-g.

Figure 1 - SEM micrographs and corresponding EDX elemental mapping of (a-b) as-deposited CIG precursor (S0) and (c-d) after thermal treatment at 450 °C (S450). The insets show a zoom into the central area of each micro-precursor. (e-f) SEM images indicating EDX measurement points on S0 and S450, respectively. (g) Elemental composition at each point, illustrating the distribution of Cu, In and Ga. EDX measurements were performed at 10 kV.

1 To further investigate the structural changes in the intermetallic CIG precursor film, XRD
 2 analysis was performed before and after thermal treatment. The CIG precursor was deposited
 3 on an unstructured SLG/SiO_xN_y substrate and thermally treated at 450 °C. The XRD patterns
 4 of the as-deposited (T0) and treated (T450) CIG precursors are shown in Fig. 2. Phase
 5 assignment was determined by comparison of 2θ position and *d*-spacing values with standard
 6 ICDD PDF database (Table 1). Although XRD measurements were not feasible for micro-
 7 absorbers, the analysis of unstructured samples can provide insights into the structural
 8 evolution of the CIG precursor before and after thermal treatment.

9 Several diffraction peaks corresponding to Mo (PDF 5-641), In (PDF 5-642), Cu (PDF 4-16-
 10 6874), Cu_{0.93}In_{0.06} (PDF 4-21-6624), Cu₁₁In₉ (PDF 41-883), and Cu_{0.817}Ga_{0.183} (PDF 4-16-6875)
 11 phases were observed. Notably, peaks associated with elemental Cu and CuGa compound
 12 appeared only after thermal treatment. The diffraction peaks located at 40.3° and at ~73.3°,
 13 present in both samples, correspond to Mo. The XRD patterns reveal that the as-deposited film
 14 primarily consists of elemental In and Cu-In compounds. No peaks indicating elemental Cu or

1 CuGa compounds were found in the as-deposited film. The dominant peak at $2\theta \sim 32.93^\circ$ can
 2 be attributed to both elemental In and a $\text{Cu}_{11}\text{In}_9$ phase due to overlapping diffraction angles (at
 3 $2\theta \sim 32.96^\circ$ and 32.95° , respectively). However, this dominant peak disappeared after thermal
 4 treatment, and two new $\text{Cu}_{11}\text{In}_9$ peaks appeared at 35° and 37.89° . This suggests possible phase
 5 decomposition or elemental redistribution during annealing, as Cu-In compounds can
 6 decompose into elemental Cu and In or form Cu- and In-rich phases, while In can diffuse into
 7 the film, reacting and forming new Cu-In phases. Additionally, the peak at 42.91° , associated
 8 with the CuIn compound in the as-deposited film, split into two new peaks at 42.76° 2θ and
 9 43.19° upon thermal treatment, assigned to $\text{Cu}_{0.817}\text{Ga}_{0.183}$ and elemental Cu, respectively. The
 10 crystallite size of the precursor was estimated using Scherrer's equation, considering all
 11 relevant peaks. The results revealed a decrease in the crystallite sizes upon annealing, from
 12 (48 ± 17) nm to (32 ± 7) nm.

Figure 2 - XRD patterns of as-deposited (T0, gray line) and thermally treated (T450, green line) CIG precursor on a flat, unstructured substrate.

1 *Table 1 - Values of 2θ and d-spacing of investigated films. The phases indexed to the data are shown with ICDD database 2θ*
2 *position, intensities (in parentheses) and d-spacing. The highlighted text shows the ICDD PDF data corresponding to the*
3 *obtained data: bold for T0 and T450; underline for T0, and italic for T450.*

Obtained data				ICDD PDF database									
T0		T450		In		Cu _{0.93} In _{0.06}		Cu ₁₁ In ₉		Cu		Cu _{0.817} Ga _{0.183}	
2θ (°)	d (Å)	2θ (°)	d (Å)	2θ (°)	d (Å)	2θ (°)	d (Å)	2θ (°)	d (Å)	2θ (°)	d (Å)	2θ (°)	d (Å)
29.976	2.979	29.860	2.990	-	-	-	-	29.827 (50)	2.993	-	-	-	-
32.931	2.718	-	-	<u>32.964</u> <u>(100)</u>	<u>2.715</u>	-	-	<u>32.951</u> <u>(80)</u>	<u>2.716</u>	-	-	-	-
-	-	35.001	2.562	36.327 (21)	2.471	-	-	34.371 (50)	2.607	-	-	-	-
36.316	2.472	36.340	2.470	36.327 (21)	2.471	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	37.890	2.373	-	-	-	-	37.751 (20)	2.381	-	-	-	-
39.132	2.300	39.115	2.301	39.169 (36)	2.298	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
42.912	2.106	42.760	2.113	-	-	<u>42.917</u> <u>(100)</u>	<u>2.105</u>	42.632 (60)	2.119	43.193 (100)	2.092	<u>42.757</u> <u>(100)</u>	<u>2.113</u>
-	-	43.197	2.093	-	-	<u>42.917</u> <u>(100)</u>	<u>2.105</u>	42.632 (60)	2.119	<u>43.193</u> <u>(100)</u>	<u>2.092</u>	<u>42.757</u> <u>(100)</u>	<u>2.113</u>
67.001	1.396	67.040	1.395	67.032 (23)	1.395	-	-	68.309 (20)	1.372	-	-	-	-
69.064	1.359	-	-	<u>69.113</u> <u>(11)</u>	<u>1.358</u>	-	-	69.581 (30)	1.350	-	-	-	-

4 3.2 Characterization of micro-CIGSe absorbers

5 The micro-CIGSe absorber was successfully formed using a single-stage selenization
6 at 480 °C, without any damage, e.g. blisters, cracks, or delamination, to the absorber or to the
7 SiO_x matrix (Fig. 3). Compared to S0_CIGSe, S450_CIGSe exhibits a rougher surface with the
8 presence of a few growth defects distributed across its surface (Fig. 3b). In both samples,
9 S0_CIGSe and S450_CIGSe, the surface analysis indicated a Cu-rich film, which becomes Cu-
10 poor when analyzed at 20 kV. This Cu surface enrichment suggests Cu diffused toward the
11 surface during selenization, potentially leading to the formation of secondary Cu-based phases
12 [38]. After selenization, any Ga content was either undetected or present in very low amount,
13 as reflected in the GGI ratio, indicating Ga segregation near the Mo back contact. A summary
14 of the elemental compositions is presented in Table 2. Surface analysis of a grown defect in
15 the S0_CIGSe sample revealed similar atomic composition to the surrounding film surface, as
16 shown in Fig. 3e-f. Notably, no Ga was detected within the defect, while the film's surface
17 contained a very low Ga concentration of 0.23 at%.

18 The GGI gradient formation is strongly influenced by diffusion processes, which depend on
19 the deposition process and temperature [39–41], Se supply [42] and Na incorporation [43]. In
20 sequential absorber synthesis, such as the selenization applied here, achieving a homogeneous
21 Ga gradient throughout the film thickness is challenging due to Ga segregation towards the
22 back contact, resulting in lower front bandgap and reduced open-circuit voltage [38,44].
23 Additionally, Na plays an important role in CIGSe absorber growth, by passivating grain
24 boundaries and surfaces, enhancing Ga diffusion and improving solar cell efficiency
25 [38,45,46]. Na can be incorporated into the absorber either during the growth process or

1 through PDT [43,47,48]. However, the SiO_xN_y Na barrier effectively blocks Na diffusion from
 2 the SLG substrate, and no PDT was performed, preventing its beneficial effects on the CIGSe
 3 absorber properties.

Figure 3 - SEM micrographs and EDX elemental maps of: (a-b) one-stage selenization of CIG precursor ($S0_CIGSe$) and (c-d) thermal treatment CIG precursor followed by one-stage selenization ($S450_CIGSe$). (e-f) SEM image and respective elemental composition of highlighted areas in sample $S450_CIGSe$.

1 Table 2 - Elemental compositions of the as-deposited and treated CIG precursors, and CIGSe films at 10 kV* and 20 kV.

T (°C)	Composition (at%)				Ratio	
	Cu	In	Ga	Se	CGI	GGI
S0 (as-deposited)	42±1.2	44±1.4	14±1.5	-	0.74±0.04	0.24±0.02
S450	41±1.2	47±1.4	12±1.0	-	0.70±0.03	0.21±0.02
S0_CIGSe	20±2.3	26±2.7	1±1.0	53±1.5	0.76±0.13	0.03±0.04
S0_CIGSe*	28±1.7	22±2.2	2±0.1	46±2.1	1.15±0.17	0.08±0.03
S450_CIGSe	21±0.7	26±1.2	1±0.6	51±0.7	0.81±0.06	0.04±0.02
S450_CIGSe*	28±1.2	25±1.2	1±0.6	46±1.2	1.08±0.08	0.02±0.02

2 Raman spectroscopy was performed to verify the vibrational modes of the crystalline structure
3 and possible phases present at the micro-absorber surface. The main vibrational modes of
4 CuInSe₂ (CIGSe) and CIGSe in Raman spectroscopy are characterized by peaks in the range of
5 170 – 180 cm⁻¹, with a dominant A₁ mode at approximately 174 cm⁻¹ for CIGSe and 177 cm⁻¹ for
6 CIGSe with GGI = 0.3 [49,50]. The average Raman spectra (Fig. 4) revealed a sharp peak at
7 170 cm⁻¹ for S0_CIGSe, corresponding to the A₁ vibrational mode of I-III-VI₂ chalcopyrite
8 compounds along with two broad bands at 207 and 224 cm⁻¹ that can be attributed to B₂/E
9 modes. For S450_CIGSe, the A₁ mode peak shifted to 171 cm⁻¹, and the B₂/E mode peaks
10 appeared at 209 and 227 cm⁻¹, indicating a slight blue shift with respect to sample S0_CIGSe.
11 The broad, low-intensity peaks in the 205-230 cm⁻¹ spectral range can be attributed to the B₂/E
12 vibrational modes of CIGSe [50,51] and CIGSe [49,52]. Interestingly, no peak associated with
13 Cu_{2-x}Se secondary phase, typically observed around 250 cm⁻¹, was detected. However, both
14 samples exhibited a significant red shift from the typical A₁ mode position of CIGSe (174 cm⁻¹)
15 and CIGSe (177 cm⁻¹). This could be an indication of a tensile stress in the grown material and
16 poor recrystallization at 480 °C [50,53]. Although Raman analysis corroborates the EDX
17 results, confirming minimal to no Ga incorporated in the micro-CIGSe absorbers, further in-
18 depth characterization is needed to validate these findings and determine the underlying cause.
19 The main hypotheses are that Ga diffused and accumulated at the back contact, and the low
20 process temperature was insufficient for its incorporation into the CIGSe lattice.

Figure 4 – Average Raman spectrum of CIGSe micro-absorber for S0_CIGSe (blue) and S450_CIGSe (red).

1 XRD patterns obtained for unstructured CIGSe films, with and without precursor thermal
 2 treatment, are shown in Fig. 5. Both samples exhibited diffraction peaks corresponding to the
 3 chalcopyrite CIGSe structure, specifically the (112), (103), and (220/204) planes (PDF 04-023-
 4 2857). A secondary Cu_{2-x}Se phase was identified in both films at approximately 52.4° . In the
 5 thermally treated film, an additional low-intensity diffraction peak appeared at $\sim 56.6^\circ$,
 6 corresponding to the CIGSe (312/116) plane, which indicates improved phase development.
 7 The presence of shoulders near the (112) and (220/204) peaks suggest the possible presence of
 8 secondary phases. It must be noted that while the (220/204) peak was primarily attributed to
 9 the CIGSe phase, overlapping contributions from Cu_{2-x}Se or CIGSe cannot be excluded due to
 10 their similar diffraction angles.
 11 Further analysis of the (112) peak revealed a decrease in the full width at half maximum
 12 (FWHM) and an increase in intensity when thermal treatment was applied to the precursor,
 13 indicating enhanced crystallinity of the unstructured CIGSe absorber. The crystallite size,
 14 estimated using the Scherrer equation, increased from 72.2 nm to 124 nm, further confirming
 15 the improvement in structural quality. In sequential absorber growth, the quality of the final
 16 CIGSe absorber strongly depends on the precursor [54–56] and selenization conditions [57,58].
 17 Regmi *et al.* [59,60] reported that increasing the selenization temperature from 450°C to 550°C ,
 18 along with extending its duration from 30 to 60 min, led to enhanced structural and
 19 morphological properties of CIGSe absorbers, and improved photovoltaic performance. Note
 20 that the crystallization behavior of micro-CIGSe films grown on pre-structured substrates
 21 might not be identical to that of unstructured substrates due to the influence of the SiO_x matrix
 22 geometry, local stress and strain, and selenization dynamics. Nevertheless, the analysis of
 23 unstructured films provides valuable information on the possible phases present in the CIGSe
 24 absorber.

Figure 5 - XRD patterns of unstructured CIGSe films (a) broad spectra and focused spectra for preferential (b) (112) plane.

25 3.3 Characterization of micro-CIGSe solar cells

26 Electrical characterization of the micro-devices was performed by current density-voltage
 27 (J-V) characteristics under AM1.5 standard one sun illumination. Out of 16 micro solar cells
 28 fabricated in each sample, S0_CIGSe produced 13 working micro-devices and S450_CIGSe
 29 produced 15. Prior to window layer deposition, Kapton tape stripes were used to isolate the
 30 micro-cells as illustrated in Fig. 6a. After depositing the i-ZnO and ZnO:Al layers, the tape was

1 removed (Fig. 6b). For the solar simulator measurement, the probes were placed on the window
 2 layer near the micro solar cell, as shown in Fig. 6c.

Figure 6 - (a) Sample with Kapton tape matrix before window layer deposition; (b) resulting matrix after window deposition; (c) probes position on the window layer during solar simulator measurement.

3 The photovoltaic parameters and statistical analysis for S0_CIGSe and S450_CIGSe are
 4 presented in Table 3 and Fig. 7, respectively. The data reveal an increase in PCE for the micro-
 5 CIGSe solar cells with thermal treatment (S450_CIGSe), primarily due to a significant
 6 improvement in open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and a slight increase in the short-current density
 7 (J_{sc}). The average improvements were 63 mV in V_{oc} , and 1.8 mA/cm² in J_{sc} , suggesting reduced
 8 recombination losses within the CIGSe bulk and at its interfaces, as well as better carrier
 9 collection compared to S0_CIGSe, likely due to better interface properties, reduced defects
 10 density and improved absorber quality. However, both samples exhibit high series resistance
 11 and extremely low shunt resistance. Typically, series resistance are below 1.5 Ω .cm² and the
 12 shunt resistance ranges from 1000 Ω .cm² to M Ω .cm². The high series resistance is likely due
 13 to the absorber bulk resistance and poor front contact, whereas the low shunt resistance
 14 suggests shunt paths caused by defects in the absorber and at its interfaces. While areas of
 15 exposed Mo were observed after thermal treatment, no such exposure was seen following the
 16 selenization. Nonetheless, the presence of such defects can result in a non-uniform p-n junction
 17 and create shunt paths, which increase leakage currents and reduce the shunt resistance, leading
 18 to lower V_{oc} and FF, ultimately degrading device performance. Additionally, the J-V
 19 characteristics of the micro solar cells (Fig. 8) show that both devices exhibit a diode-like
 20 behavior with significant impact of series and shunt resistances, which primarily affects the
 21 fill factor (FF), but can also reduce the J_{sc} and V_{oc} [61].

22 Table 3 - Photovoltaic parameters for micro-CIGSe solar cells S0_CIGSe and S450_CIGSe selenized at 480 °C.

Sample		PCE (%)	V_{oc} (mV)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	FF (%)	R_s (Ω .cm ²)	R_{sh} (Ω .cm ²)
S0_CIGSe	Average	0.35±0.32	176±25	6.7±4.3	26.3±1.6	35±22	41±26
S450_CIGSe	Average	0.56±0.35	239±26	8.5±4.4	26.0±2.8	37±21	39±14

1 Since the Na barrier prevented Na diffusion from the SLG substrate - offering no enhancement
 2 to the CIGSe film quality or electronic properties - and Ga likely accumulated near the back
 3 contact, reducing the front bandgap and V_{oc} [38,44], the observed improvements can be
 4 attributed to the thermal treatment applied before selenization. The thermal treatment likely
 5 enhanced the precursor uniformity and interdiffusion, resulting in a more homogeneous surface
 6 (as seen in Fig. 1c) and a CIGSe absorber with better crystallinity and electronic properties
 7 compared to sample S0_CIGSe. To further enhance micro-CIGSe solar cell performance, Na
 8 PDT and higher selenization temperatures could improve crystallinity, Ga incorporation, and
 9 defect passivation. Moreover, mitigating Ga segregation at the CIGSe/Mo interface is crucial
 10 and can be achieved by introducing Se during precursor deposition [62] or optimizing the
 11 selenization process [42,44].

Figure 7 – Solar cell parameters of micro-CIGSe solar cells grown by one-stage selenization of as-deposited CIG precursor (S0_CIGSe, blue) and thermally treated CIG precursor (S450_CIGSe, red): (a) Open-circuit voltage, (b) short-circuit density, (c) power conversion efficiency, (d) fill factor, (e) series resistance, and (f) shunt resistance.

Figure 8 - JV characteristics under 1 sun illumination of (a) S0_CIGSe and (b) S450_CIGSe micro solar cells. Representative JV curves for (a, bold) S0_CIGSe and (b, bold) S450_CIGSe micro solar cells, with efficiencies of 0.32 % and 0.55%, respectively.

1 4. Conclusions

2 This study investigates the effects of thermal treatment on micro-CIGSe solar cells fabricated on pre-
 3 structured substrates with SiO_xN_y Na barrier and without PDT. Our results show that both the as-
 4 deposited and annealed CIG precursors were Cu-poor, with CGI ratios of 0.74 and 0.70, respectively.
 5 The thermal treatment improved precursor morphology, resulting in a smoother surface compared to
 6 the as-deposited film. After selenization, sample S450_CIGSe exhibited a few growth defects and both
 7 films remained Cu-poor, with CGI of 0.81 for S450_CIGSe, while S0_CIGSe had CGI of 0.76, close
 8 to the as-deposited composition. However, both samples showed minimal Ga incorporation into the
 9 CIGSe lattice, suggesting Ga segregation near the back contact. Raman analysis revealed dominant A1
 10 mode peaks at 170 cm^{-1} for S0_CIGSe and 171 cm^{-1} for S450_CIGSe, consistent with the vibrational
 11 modes of I-III-VI₂ chalcopyrite compounds. Device characterization confirmed that thermal treatment
 12 in average led to an increase in V_{oc} from 176 (S0_CIGSe) to 239 mV (S450_CIGSe), likely due to better
 13 interface properties, improved absorber quality and reduced recombination losses, achieving an average
 14 efficiency of $(0.56 \pm 0.35)\%$, with the best performing micro solar cell reaching PCE of 1.44%.

15 Future work should focus on improving device performance by (1) optimizing micro-CIGSe absorber
 16 growth (e.g. selenization temperature, Ga grading, and Na PDT) to enhance material quality and
 17 interface passivation, (2) improving the CdS buffer layer to reduce recombination losses, and (3)
 18 optimizing ZnO:Al front contact layer and implementing a metallic grid to improve current collection
 19 and reduce resistive losses.

20

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28

1 **Data availability statement**

2 All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article.

3

4 **Conflict of interest**

5 The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

6

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